

Synthesis, characterization and biological studies on some transition metal complexes derived from a heterocyclic Schiff base ligand

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Abstract : Schiff base ligand (L) derived from pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and L(+)-alanine and its Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, IR, electronic spectra and magnetic measurements. The elemental analysis data show that the complexes have composition ML₂. The low molar conductance values reveal that all the complexes are non-electrolytes. IR data demonstrate that the Schiff base act as a bidentate donor through the azomethine nitrogen and carboxylato oxygen atoms. The electronic spectral and magnetic measurements indicate that Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have tetrahedral and Cu^{II} complex has square planar geometry. The antimicrobial activity of synthesized ligand and its complexes were screened against the bacterial species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and the fungal species *Candida albicans*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhizoctonia bataicola* by disc diffusion method. The antimicrobial activity data show that the metal complexes are more active than the ligand. The nuclease activity of the metal complexes indicates the complexes to be capable of cleaving CT DNA in the presence of oxidant.

Keywords : IR, electronic spectra, magnetic, antimicrobial activity, DNA.

Introduction

Metal ions play important roles in the synthesis and transport of organic molecules in living organisms, and in catalyzing acid-base and redox processes in biological systems. Transition metals play a key role in biological systems such as cell division, respiration, nitrogen fixation and photosynthesis. The presence of transition metals in human blood plasma indicates their importance in the mechanism for accumulated storage and transport of transition metals in living organisms¹. Many reports are available about the chemical, structural and biological properties of Schiff base-metal complexes². Chelating ligands containing O and N donor atoms show broad biological activity and are of special interest because of the variety of ways in which they are bonded to metal ions. Literature indicates that biological activity of amino acid-Schiff base complexes have scarcely been investigated³⁻⁸. Recently, we have synthesized and characterized some Schiff base metal complexes and their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities have been investigated^{9,10}. In the present study we report the synthesis, characterization and bio-

logical studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff base derived from pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde and L(+)-alanine.

Results and discussion

The Schiff base ligand is soluble in common organic solvents. All the complexes are soluble in DMF and DMSO and insoluble in other common organic solvents. The analytical data, physical properties of the ligand and its complexes are listed in Table 1. The analytical data (Table 1) indicate that the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 2 for all the complex systems. The molar conductance of all the complexes was measured in DMSO using 10⁻³ M solutions at room temperature. The low molar conductance data (3.1–9.7 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) showed them as non-electrolytes¹¹.

Infrared spectra :

The important IR spectral data of the ligand and its complexes are given in Table 2. The IR spectrum of the free Schiff base ligand exhibits a broad band centered at 1646 cm⁻¹, due to azomethine group ν(C=N)¹². On

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic data of the Schiff base ligand and its complexes

Compd.	Empirical formula and colour	Elemental analysis (%) :			Magnetic moment (B.M.)
		Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	
K(L)	C ₈ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ K	47.04 (47.11)	4.44 (4.35)	13.71 (13.66)	-
[CoL ₂]	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ Co	49.37 (49.31)	4.66 (4.59)	16.44 (16.38)	4.23
[NiL ₂]	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ Ni	49.40 (49.35)	4.66 (4.61)	16.45 (16.39)	3.42
[CuL ₂]	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cu	48.79 (49.71)	4.61 (4.55)	16.25 (16.11)	1.84
[ZnL ₂]	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ Zn	48.56 (48.49)	4.58 (4.51)	16.17 (16.23)	-

Table 2. Infrared spectral data of ligand and its complexes (cm⁻¹)

Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
K(L)	1646	1595	1388	-	-
[CoL ₂]	1631	1587	1397	527	440
[NiL ₂]	1634	1583	1380	532	435
[CuL ₂]	1629	1578	1379	511	443
[ZnL ₂]	1637	1574	1375	519	450

complexation the position of this band was shifted to lower frequency in the $\sim 1629\text{--}1637\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ion. For the free ligand, the observed bands at 1595 and 1388 cm^{-1} can be respectively ascribed to asymmetric carboxyl $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and symmetric carboxyl $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ groups. During complexation they were shifted to lower frequency by $\sim 5\text{--}7\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the linkage between the metal ion and carboxylato oxygen atom. The large difference between the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ ($\sim 200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates the monodentate binding nature of the carboxylato group¹³ in the complexes. In the lower frequency region the new weak bands observed at 510–520 and 450–420 cm^{-1} have been assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibrations¹², respectively.

Magnetic properties :

The present Co^{II} complex has a magnetic moment of 4.23 B.M., which is in agreement with the reported value^{14,15} of 4.2–4.8 B.M. for tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes. Generally, square planar Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic, while tetrahedral complexes have moments in the range 3.2–4.1 B.M. The Ni^{II} complex reported herein has a room temperature magnetic moment value of 3.42 B.M., which is within the range observed for tetrahedral Ni^{II}

complex. Cu^{II} square planar complexes exhibit magnetic moments in the range^{14,15} 1.8–2.1 B.M. These values are slightly higher than the spin-only value of 1.72 B.M., due to spin-orbit coupling followed by lowering of symmetry.

Electronic spectra :

In the electronic spectrum of the Schiff base, the band observed at 303 nm can be attributed to $\pi\text{--}\pi^*$ transition of the azomethine chromophore. In the spectra of the complexes, this band is shifted to $\sim 290\text{ nm}$, indicating the azomethine nitrogen to be involved in coordination with metal ion.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex displays only one absorption band in the visible region at 607 nm, due to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition¹⁶. This indicates tetrahedral geometry for the complex. The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex shows an intense absorption band at 541 nm for the ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ transition indicating its tetrahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex exhibits a broad band centered at 609 nm due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition corresponding to square planar geometry¹⁶.

From the results obtained from elemental analysis, conductance, infrared, electronic and magnetic moment studies, the probable structure of the complexes under investigation are given in Fig. 1.

(b) Square planar geometry for Cu^{II} complex**Fig. 1.** Proposed structure of the metal complexes.

Antimicrobial activity :

The results of the antibacterial and antifungal activities are summarized in Tables 3a and b. The Schiff base ligand shows moderate activity against all organisms, whereas the complexes are more active than that of the

Table 3a. Minimum inhibitory concentration of the synthesized compounds against the growth of bacteria ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
K(L)	79	72	59	86	94
[CoL ₂]	42	44	32	65	52
[NiL ₂]	38	42	54	52	60
[CuL ₂]	36	28	26	40	34
[ZnL ₂]	64	38	46	72	48
Chloroam-phenicol ^a	4	8	10	6	12

^aStandard.

Table 3b. Minimum inhibitory concentration of the synthesised compounds against the growth of fungi ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Comnd	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>R. stolonifer</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>R. bataicola</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
K(L)	62	68	82	85	68
[CoL ₂]	52	56	42	76	60
[NiL ₂]	46	52	38	72	52
[CuL ₂]	38	46	30	44	40
[ZnL ₂]	48	50	56	64	61
Nystatin ^a	10	16	8	12	14

^aStandard.

Schiff base ligand. Among the complexes, Cu^{II} complex is highly active against the bacterial and fungal species compared with some known standards. The mechanism of toxicity of the complexes with the ligand may be ascribed to the increase in the lipophilic nature of the complexes arising from chelation¹⁷. Chelation reduces the polarity of the metal atom mainly because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possible π -electron delocalization within the whole chelate ring. Also the chelation increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which subsequently favours the permeation through the lipid layer of cell membrane.

The activity increases with increase in concentration of test solution containing the complexes because it is well known that concentration plays a vital role in increasing the degree of inhibition of antibacterial growth. It is suggested that the complexes having antimicrobial activity may act either by killing the microbe or by inhi-

biting multiplication of the microbe by blocking their active sites¹⁸. The mode of action of antimicrobials may involve different targets in pathogens, e.g. interference with the cell wall synthesis and damage to the cytoplasmic membrane, as a result of which cell permeability may be, altered leading to cell death. The enhanced activity of the complexes can also be explained on the basis of their high solubility, fineness of the particles, size of the metal ion and the presence of bulkier organic moieties. The preliminary results indicate that chemotherapeutic agents used experimentally and clinically are potential metal based antimicrobial agents, as the metal is best transported in the cell in chelated form¹⁹. Further, it increases the delocalization π -electrons over the whole chelate ring and enhances the lipophilicity of the complexes. This increased lipophilicity enhances the penetration of the complexes into lipid membrane and restricts further multiplicity of the microorganisms.

DNA cleavage study :

The nuclease activity of the complexes in the presence of H₂O₂ has been studied using CT DNA in the medium of tris-HCl buffer containing NaCl (pH 7.2). Nuclease activity exhibited by certain transition metal complexes in the presence of hydrogen peroxide is attributed to the participation of hydroxyl radical in DNA cleavage. Fig. 2 shows the electrophoretic pattern of CT DNA treated with complex. Cleavage experiments suggest that untreated DNA and the incubated DNA with either complex or

Lane 1 : Control DNA; Lane 2 : DNA + Co^{II} + H₂O₂; Lane 3 : DNA + Ni^{II} + H₂O₂; Lane 4 : DNA + Cu^{II} + H₂O₂; Lane 5 : DNA + Zn^{II} + H₂O₂

Fig. 2. Agarose gel (%) showing the results of electrophoresis pattern of CT DNA with metal complexes.

peroxide alone did not show any significant DNA cleavage. However, in the presence of peroxide, the complexes were found to exhibit cleavage activity and among the four complexes copper complex (Lane 4) exhibit higher activity cleavage.

Experimental

L(+)-alanine and pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde were obtained from Fluka and Lancaster. Metal(II) chlorides were purchased from Merck. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Solvents were purified and distilled before use. The metal content in the complexes was determined by EDTA titration. Elemental analysis was obtained using a Perkin-Elmer elemental analyzer. Conductivity measurements were carried out on 10^{-3} M solutions in DMSO at room temperature with a coronation digital conductivity meter. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellet on a JASCO FT/IR-410 spectrometer in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The room temperature magnetic measurements were carried out using Guoy's balance and the diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constant. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-25 UV/Vis spectrometer.

Synthesis of Schiff base ligand :

To a solution of L(+)-alanine (2 mmol) in MeOH containing KOH (2 mmol), pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde (2 mmol) in MeOH was added. The above mixture was magnetically stirred and refluxed for 1 h. The volume of yellow solution was then reduced *in vacuo*. Anhydrous Et_2O was added to precipitate the Schiff base and the product obtained was recrystallized from EtOH (yield : 77%).

Synthesis of metal complexes :

Metal(II) chloride (1 mmol) was dissolved in MeOH and the solution was filtered and added dropwise into methanolic solution of Schiff base ligand (2 mmol). The above mixture was magnetically stirred and refluxed for 1 h. The complexes obtained were filtered, washed with MeOH and dried *in vacuo* (yield : 55–67%).

In vitro antimicrobial activity :

The Schiff base ligand and its complexes were tested against the bacterial species *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. vulgaris* and *P. aeruginosa*, and the fungal species *C. albicans*, *R. stolonifer*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger*

and *R. bataticola*. These studies were carried out using disc diffusion method^{20,21}. Chloroamphenicol was used as the standard antibacterial agent whereas Nystatin was used as the standard antifungal agent. The test organisms were grown on nutrient agar medium in petri plates. The compounds were prepared in DMSO and soaked in filter paper disc of 5 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness. The discs were placed on the previously seeded plates and incubated at 37 °C and the diameter of inhibition zone around each disc was measured after 24 h for bacterial and 72 h for fungal species. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by serial dilution technique.

DNA cleavage study :

Gel electrophoresis cleavage reactions were run between the metal complexes and the DNA, and the solutions were diluted with loading dye using 1% agarose gel. The solution was heated to boiling to dissolve agarose completely. Then 3 μl of ethidium bromide (0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was added to the above solution and mixed well. The warmed agarose was poured and clamped immediately with comb to form sample wells. The gel was mounted into electrophoretic tank. The DNA sample (30 μm), 50 μm metal complex, 500 μm H_2O_2 in 50 mm tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.1) were mixed with loading dye and loaded into the well of the submerged gel using a micropipette. The electric current was passed into running buffer. After electrophoresis, the gel was photographed under UV transluminator and documented.

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